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1.3 GHz Nb-coated cavity irradiated by laser in argon atmosphere and RF tested

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ABSTRACT

This is Task 9.5 milestone report MS 41 A facility for laser operation for complex 3D treatment is tested on 1.3 GHz cavity.

A facility for laser operation for complex 3D treatment had been designed and built by RTU team, the operation software written by C#(C sharp) language.

Then the facility was tested for uniformity of Nd:YAG laser treatment with optical microscope and AFM.

Then, we performed a series of treatments of Nb-coated curved surfaces.

The first, the cylindrical copper tubes with Nb thin film were irradiated using the Nd:YAG laser in the chamber with an Ar gas. The irradiated samples' surface roughness (Ra) decreased by more than ten times. The cracks on the irradiated surface of samples decreased in size.

The morphology of irradiated and non-irradiated surfaces was studied by optical microscope and AFM. Irradiated the inner surface of cylindrical Nb on Cu samples by the Nd:YAG laser radiation leads to improve of adhesion and Nb surface roughness. UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), Dr. R. Valizadeh. Partner deposited Nb on Cu tubular samples. Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), Dr. C. Pira. Partner prepared Cu tubular samples. After laser irradiation of the sample, the roughness parameters Ra decreased by about an order of magnitude of 900 nm till 90 nm. The second, the spherical RF cavity with Nb thin film on Cu substrate preparing by Dr. Reza Valizadeh from UKRI were irradiated using the Nd:YAG laser in the chamber with an Ar gas. Irradiation of the 3D spherical part of the RF cavity by the laser shows that the deposition of Nb thin film on the Cu substrate is nonhomogeneous. Nb coating on the 2D tubular part of the RF cavity is thick, but on the 3D spheric part, it is too thin, less than 1 mk. Therefore, the 3D spheric part has not changed.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The spherical RF cavity with Nb thin film on Cu substrate from UKRI were irradiated using the Nd:YAG laser in the chamber with an Ar gas. Irradiation of the 3D spherical part of the RF cavity by the laser shows that the deposition of Nb thin film on the Cu substrate is nonhomogeneous. Nb coating on the 2D tubular part of the RF cavity is thick, but on the 3D spheric part, it is too thin, less than 1 μk . Therefore, the 3D spheric part has not changed. Irradiation of the 3D spherical part of the RF cavity by the Nd:YAG laser shows that the deposition of Nb thin film on the Cu substrate is nonhomogeneous. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare the RF cavity with homogeneous Nb deposition on Cu at low temperature and Nb thickness from 3 μk to 10 μk .

1 Introduction

In superconducting RF cavities for particle accelerators, the Nb thin film coated on Cu (Nb/Cu) structure is one of the alternatives to bulk Nb RF cavities. However, R&D is required to achieve reproducible performance of Nb/Cu RF cavities, which should be comparable to bulk Nb. Since only a few μm of superconducting material is required in the RF cavity, the bulk of the RF cavity acts as a mechanical support for the structure. Therefore, one can use structural material such as Cu, which is cheaper and has higher thermal conductivity than Nb. There are three challenges associated with Cu structure coated with Nb film: (1) the Nb film adhesion, (2) the quality of Nb/Cu interface, and (3) the mechanical strength of Cu. The adhesion and the quality of the Nb/Cu interface can be improved by deposition at elevated temperatures and by using HiPIMS deposition. However, the higher temperature results in softening of Cu, which may ultimately affect the mechanical integrity of the cavity and suppress the Q-factor slope, as has been shown in [1]. As shown in our previous work [2, 3], nanosecond laser annealing of the Nb/Cu structure after Nb thin film deposition on Cu substrate allows for an increase in the grain size of Nb and improves interfacial adhesion. This allows thin film deposition at a lower temperature where the mechanical integrity of the Cu cavity is not compromised. In this process, only a thin layer of Cu is heated, so the mechanical strength of the bulk material is not affected.

2 Description of laser facility

2.1 BASIC CONCEPT

Laser facility for irradiation inner surface of RF cavity: principal schematics and construction of Ar gas chamber is shown in Fig. 1.

2.2 BUILDING THE FACILITY

Construction of chamber with Ar gas and Nd:YAG laser was built in the Laboratory of Semiconductor Physics, RTU, for irradiation of a tubular part of the RF cavity and both tubular and spherical parts of the RF cavity.

In an Ar gas chamber with an optical window, where a linear stepper motor (Z. coordinate) and a motorized rotating platform (α . coordinate) were installed. A miniature rotation stage for mirror rotation (β . coordinate) is installed.

Dimensions of the RF cavity in gas chamber:

L=450mm, D=250mm, the Ar gas atmosphere 1.5 atm pressure.

Figure 1. Principal schematics of Laser facility for irradiation inner surface of RF cavity.

2.3 SOFTWARE

The developed control program for laser irradiation of the RF cavity consists of two parts.

Program for irradiation of the tubular part of the RF cavity. The control is carried out on 2D coordinates: Z and α , which provide the movement of the beam along the spiral with the change of the spiral pitch or speed of rotation.

2.4 TESTING THE FACILITY OPERATION WITH A Nb COATED SAMPLE

The operation of the facility was tested with Nb coated tubular sample and reported in Milestone report MS41.

3 Coating copper cavity with a Nb

Seamless copper 1.3 GHz cavities for this work were produced by Piccoli. The manufacturing process was optimised during IFAS WP9. Two cavities that are not equipped with flanges were provided for surface polishing at INFN, Nb coating at UKRI and following laser treatment at RTU. These cavities are not equipped with flanges. Thus, they are well fit for the purpose of testing all technological steps. But they are not suitable for RF testing at LHe as cannot be sealed.

It should be noted that in the original WP9 project there was the second cavity provider, PTI from Belarus. PTI should be providing EB welding of flanges for cavities produced by Piccoli as well as welded cavities produced by hydroforming. However, the participation of partner PTI (Belarus) was suspended from IFAST in 2022 due to the EU's decision to halt collaborations with institutions in Russia and Belarus. In fact, PTI was expected to provide an in-kind contribution that could not be substituted, as production within European industry could not be accommodated within the Work Package budget. Since no replacement for PTI was found; therefore, only Piccoli produced cavity were available for Task 9.5.

3.1 CAVITY 1

Cavity 1 consists of elliptical part and one tubular part, see Fig. 2. Tubular sample has a diameter of 800 mm and a length of 200 mm.

Figure 2. Photo of construction of Ar gas chamber with controlling 3D coordinates for laser treatment with Nb coated Cavity 1 installed for laser treatment of inner surface.

Nb thin film deposition was performed at UKRI with Bipolar HiPIMS using a Nb rod as a target with the following parameters:

- Base pressure before deposition $p = 1 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar
- Chamber filled with Kr at $p = 6 \times 10^{-3}$ mbar
- HiPIMS parameters:
 - Voltage $U_{neg} = 380$ V
 - Average current $I_{av} = 800$ mA
 - Peak current $I_{peak} = 10$ A
 - Average power $P_{av} = 300$ W
 - Pulse frequency $f = 1$ kHz
 - Pulse width $\tau_{neg} = 100$ μ s
 - Positive kick:
 - $U_{pos} = 50$ V
 - Pulse duration $\tau_{pos} = 200$ μ s
 - delay $\tau_{del} = 1.5$ μ s
- Deposition duration $t = 6$ h

Figure 3 shows (a) a picture of Cavity 1 in a deposition chamber during HiPIMS deposition of Nb and (b) HiPIMS pulses.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. (a) Cavity 1 during HiPIMS deposition of Nb, (b) HiPIMS pulses.

3.2 CAVITY 2

Cavity 2 consists of elliptic part and two tubular parts, see Fig. 4. One of the tubes is equipped with a lip (see Fig. 4 (b)) while the other is a straight tube.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Cavity 2 images: (a) whole cavity, (b) a lip on a top flange.

Cavity 2 was deposited with a different technique. Nb thin film deposition was performed with Pulsed DC at UKRI with the following parameters:

- Chamber filled with Kr at $p = 2 \times 10^{-3}$ mbar
- Pulsed DC parameters:
 - Voltage $U_{neg} = 480$ V
 - Average current $I_{av} = 830$ mA
 - Average power $P_{av} = 400$ W
 - Pulse frequency $f = 350$ kHz
 - Pulse width $\tau_{neg} = 1.1$ μ s.
- Deposition duration $t = 8$ h

The cavity was manually moved along Z-axis. Procedure is repeated over several days to maximise film thickness. Pressure and plasma parameters were kept constant during deposition. Figure 6 shows (a) a picture of Cavity 2 in a deposition chamber during Pulsed DC deposition.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Cavity 2 during Pulsed DC deposition of Nb

After deposition the cavity was vented to air and inspected visually showing smooth film coating without delamination and visible defects, see Fig. 6.

After depositions Cavities 1 and 2 were shipped to RTU.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Cavity 2 after deposition of Nb: (a) tubular part, (b) elliptic part.

4 Laser treatment of a Nb coated 1.3 GHz cavity

4.1 TREATMENT OF A SPHERICAL PART OF THE CAVITY 1

Figure 2 shows the first 1.3 GHz Nb coated cavity (Cavity 1) installed at the facility for laser treatment. This sample does not have a top tubular part; however, this is sufficient for testing a capability of laser treatment facility. Irradiation of the 3D spheric part of RF cavity demonstrated that facility can provide uniform laser irradiation of 3D curved surfaces and results the surface with a surface smoother than it was just after deposition.

After this run the software for the control of β coordinates was developing. It was coordinated with the previous software for α and Z coordinates.

4.2 TREATMENT OF A SPHERICAL PART OF THE CAVITY 2

Cavity was irradiated with the Nd:YAG laser with the following parameters:

- The laser intensity $I = 50 \text{ MW/cm}^2$;
- Laser beam diameter $D = 2 \text{ mm}^2$;
- Pulse frequency $f = 10 \text{ Hz}$; laser beam horizontal and vertical step is 0.4 mm.

Figure 7 shows Cavity 2 after laser treatment. The treated surface looks smoother than before the treatment.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Cavity 2 after irradiation with the Nd:YAG laser.

5 Future plans for RF testing

It was already mentioned in Section 3 that the cavities are not equipped with flanges. Thus, it is impossible to test them in the RF testing facilities with LHe. However, UKRI is presently building a new low power RF facility that is based on conductance cooling and LHe-free cryocooler. Most of the parts have been produced and are under mounting and assembly, see Fig. 8. Specially designed flanges that provide only electric and thermal conductance are under manufacturing. Conductance cooling allows to bypass the problem with vacuum seal of such a cavity by using the same vacuum in the cavity and a cryostat.

Building and operation of this facility was not a part of IFAST, its commissioning is planned for autumn 2025, but this is the only possibility to perform an RF testing of Cavity 2.

Figure 8. A new low power RF facility at UKRI: (a) a design of cavity cooled by conductance cooling assembly, (b) a cryostat inside a vacuum chamber with a cryocooler on its top.

6 Conclusions

This task within IFAST WP9 allows to reach a number of milestones:

1. A laser installation for irradiating the inner surface of a 1.3 GHz cavity has been developed, manufactured, automated and tested.
2. Two 1.3 GHz seamless copper cavities have been produced, polished, coated with Nb thin film and, finally, irradiated with a laser.
3. The irradiated inner surface of both cavities looks smoother.
4. RF testing of Cavity 2 will be performed with a facility that currently being built at UKRI but after completion of IFAST.
5. The laser facility can be employed in future for laser treatment of both Nb coated and bulk Nb cavities to improve their RF performance. It can also be used for exploring a possibility for using with other superconducting thin films.

References

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